

THE CAUSAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADERSHIP STYLES AND BOTH TASK AND CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE: INTERPERSONAL COMPETENCIES AS MEDIATORS IN THE RELATIONSHIP

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate empirically the effects of transactional and transformational leadership styles on both task and contextual performance, and the mediating role of interpersonal competencies of leaders in the relationship between predictive constructs and criterion constructs in five Libyan universities. 390 teaching members were randomly selected and filled in an online questionnaire and distributed it. 320 of 390 questionnaire were collected. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was applied to test ten hypotheses via the AMOS technique. The findings show that the transformational leadership has significant direct effect on interpersonal competencies, task performance, and contextual performance, whereas transactional leader has direct effect on task performance only. In addition, interpersonal competencies mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and both task performance and contextual performance, while it was not significant with transactional leadership and both task performance and contextual performance. These findings support the Economic and social exchange theory. Implications for future research are also discussed.

Keywords: Leadership style, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, interpersonal competencies, task and contextual performance

INTRODUCTION

The form of relationship among members within organizations is very important for both individual and organization performance. Good mutual social relations between leaders and employees are useful for employee outcomes within organizations (Krishnan, 2012), and organizational change (Al-Qura'an, 2015). Performance in organizational literature is multidimensional since all organizations alike seek to improve and develop it in different ways and means. The formal performance stipulated in the organizational description and the informal (voluntary) performance is the focus of this study. Consequently, the direct relations between the leaders and the principals of it acquire the opinions and ideas of researchers in this field. For example, organ (1988) and Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman and Fetter (1990) suggested that transformational leadership leads to improve extra-role performance, while transactional leadership closely related to in-role performance.

Today's organizations need effective leaders who understand the complexities of the rapidly changing global environment. If the task is highly structured and the leader has good relationship with the employees, effectiveness will be high on the part of the employees. Critical studies in leadership literature have conflicted over the relationship between leadership style and performance. Some opinions held that the relationship was direct (e.g., Haghi, 2016; Haghighi & Maleki, 2016; Nasra & Heilbrunn, 2015), while others assumed that the relationship was indirect. Unlike, Nohe and Hertel (2017) provided interesting finding, where the direct influence of transformational leadership on extra- role performance was negative when attitudinal and relational variables were used as mediators.

In indirect relationship analysis between leadership style and job performance, often the researchers focused on attitudinal factors as mediators such as trust in leader, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and leader- member exchange. These relations are subject to the exchange theory (Blue, 1978). Recent researchers and authors in this field suggested that emotional intelligence competencies has an important role in improving working environment. Centre for Creative Leadership reported that, 75% of careers failed due to lack of emotional skills among leaders, including inability to handle interpersonal problems and team leadership through times of distress or conflict, or inability to adapt to change or building trust (Natural HR, 2017). In current study, therefore, suggests that emotions as competencies of leader could improve the job performance. Derue, Nahrgang, Wellman, & Humphrey (2011) claimed that behaviours of leader affect traits and competencies of them. Accordingly, the researcher suggested that emotions competencies of leader could mediate the relationship between leadership style and job performance. Subsequently, this research aims to examine the direct and indirect effects of the transformational and transactional leadership on job performance in Libyan universities.

However, there are a number of justifications for conducting this study. First, the lack of consistency in the findings of previous research that examined the relationship between leadership style and job performance when interpersonal competencies mediates in that relationship. Second, empirical research in the field of leadership still gives unclear picture of the role of interpersonal competencies of the leader in dynamic interactions and encouraging employees to engage in-role and extra- role performance.

LEADERSHIP STYLE

Leadership is a social influence process in which the leader seeks the voluntary participation of subordinates in an effort to reach organization goals (Silva, 2016). A leader can be defined as a person who delegates or influencing others to act so as to carry out specified objectives. In spite of the many leadership styles that have been defined, it can be concluded that leadership is a process of social interaction where performance outcomes are strongly influenced by the leader's ability to influence the behavior of their followers (Humphrey, 2012). In this regard, interaction between two or more members of a group that often involves a structuring and the perceptions and expectations of the members (Bass, 1995). In addition, the leadership is Interaction between two or more members of a group that often involves a structuring and the

perceptions and expectations of the members (Cohen, 1990). In dynamic interactions between leaders and followers, Leader Member Exchange (LMX) theory, charismatic leadership theory, and transformational leadership theory are most common in leadership filed (Alajili, 2019). LMX theory concerns with the dyadic quality of the relationship between the leader and followers to understand the effects of the leader on the members, teams, and organisation. High- quality, trust, affects, and respect- based relationships are basis of dyadic relationship quality (Nathan, 2016). According to LMX theory, leaders form different types of relationships with specific two groups of followers. First group is in- group since its members receive considerably more attention from the leader. Second is out- group, where members do not receive the attention of the leader. An affiliation of employee's in-group or out-group depends on their work-related attitudes and behaviours towards the leader (Rockstuhl, Dulebohn, & Shore, 2012).

Charismatic leadership theory describes what to expect from both leaders and followers. Leaders engage in extraordinary behaviors and display substantial expertise and therefor, followers react to these extraordinary behaviors as part of the greater situational context and attribute charisma to the leader (Bell, 2013). Charismatic leadership theory describes key charismatic leader's behavior who advocates a vision that is highly discrepant from the status quo and inspires in unconventional ways to achieve the vision (Yuki, 2010). Charisma is defined as "a relationship between an individual (leader) and one or more followers based on leader behaviors combined with favorable attributions on the part of followers" (Waldman, Ramirez, & House, 2001, p. 135). Key behaviours on the part of the leader include articulating a vision and sense of mission, showing determination, and communicating high performance expectations (Waldman et al., 2001).

Transformational leadership theory or full range leadership theory is one of the most influential theories in leadership research (Kim & Yoon, 2015), because organisations need to superior leaders who have the ability to guidance the organisation's goals (Celik, Akgemci, & Akyazi, 2015). This theory points to a constellation of leadership style which range from transactional leadership behaviours to transformational leadership behaviours (Michel, Lyons, & Cho, 2010). The fundamental assumption of the theory is leader's ability to motivate followers to go beyond their task requirements (Trmal, Bustamam, & Mohamed, 2015).

Transactional leadership is behaviours that seek to motivate and comply followers by rewards and penalties (Sims, Faraj, & Yun, 2009), as the leaders and followers determent the conditions and amount of the work for ending it on time and provide compensation to employees and then, transactional leaders observe employees for any missteps and deviations (Martin, 2015). According to Bass (1985), two factors that characterize transactional leadership, which are contingent reward and management-by-exception (Ahangar, 2009). Contingent rewards are rewards for effort, promises rewards for good performance, recognizes accomplishments (Bass, Avolio, & Jung, 2003) whereas, management by exception that is split into two: passive and active (Bass, 1997). Management by exception (active) indicates to leaders who monitor employees' performance to ensure that goals are achieved (Greiman, 2009). For management by exception (passive), leaders interfere only when troubles have already occurred (Bono and

Judge, 2004). Transformational leaders inspire their employees to transcend their own self-interests for the good of the organisation and are capable of having a profound and extraordinary effect on their employees (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Transformational leader uses four types of behaviors, namely: idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration (Tharnpas & Sakun, 2015) and these behaviors contribute to effective leadership and positive leadership (Caillier, 2014) specifically, to motivate employee to achieve higher levels of performance (Martin, 2015).

Task and contextual performance

Task and contextual performance are two distinct dimensions of behaviour at work that can contribute independently to effectiveness outcomes for organisations (Griffin, Neal, & Neal, 2000). Both task and contextual performance describe the specific behaviours of individuals (Motowidlo et al., 1997). These behaviours can be distinguished from effectiveness, which is the impact that behaviours have on outcomes that are valued by the organisation (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997).

Task performance is refers as employee's direct or indirect involvement in the process of manufacture goods from raw material to finished goods, providing service and supporting organization important function (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). To encourage employee involvement, it should be linked to formal organization reward system. Therefore, employee needs to fulfill the requirement of organization in order to obtain the reward. In this regard, there are five models are relevant to task performance that contains specific job tasks proficiency, non-job task specific proficiency, oral and written proficiency, supervision of leadership position and management support (Campbell, 1990). Contextual performance refers to "those activities of employees that are required to interact and coordinate with others and to perform them in certain ways that go beyond their job- description in order to fulfill job specific tasks" (Jyoti & bhau, 2016, p. 82). It is important in shaping organization culture, (Werner, 2000). Contextual performance can be divided into interpersonal facilitation that able to support colleague such as cooperation and job dedication that refer to employee self-motivation such as self-discipline or follow the instruction of organization or leader.

Relevant elements of contextual performance that able to bring effectiveness are organizational citizenship behaviour (Smith, Organ, & Near, 1983) and extra-role performance (Dyne, Cummings, & Parks, 1995). In this line, Borman and Motowidlo (1993) enumerated five categories of contextual performance: a) helping and cooperating with others, b) volunteering for additional task activities, c) persisting with extra effort, d) following rules and procedures, e) and endorsing organizational objectives.

Interpersonal competencies

The competency of leadership refers to do something in effective manner, where leaders can accomplish (Yuki , 2010). Interpersonal competencies model of leadership is clearly described in the models of emotional and social intelligence, namely, ability model, mixed models, and the trait model (Masa'deh, 2016). Interpersonal competencies is oriented towards the relationship between leaders and followers, and includes two types, which are social awareness

and relationship management. Social awareness is defined by (Goleman, 1998: 88) as “ability to understand the emotional makeup of other people skill in treating people according to their emotional reactions”. Social awareness includes empathy, service orientation, developing others, leveraging diversity, and political awareness. The empathy is defined as understanding the other person’s emotions, needs and concerns. Leaders with this skill to know completely their words and acts influence employees and they know if its impact is negative, they must change it (Goldman, 2002).

Competencies of relationship management are proficiency in managing relationships and building networks and ability to find common ground and build rapport (Goleman, 1998). Hence, leader has ability to affect employees, persuading or convincing them in order to gain their support. In addition, leader develops followers by giving feedback and support. In relationship management skills, the leader possesses ability to conflict management, and inspires and guide individuals and groups to accomplish tasks as well. Furthermore, leaders who have high skills of relationship management able to create teamwork with employees work toward a shared goal; participating actively, sharing responsibility and rewards and contributing to the capability of the team (Goldstein, Princiotta, & Naglieri, 2017). Competencies of relationship management represents influence, communication, leadership, change catalyst, conflict management, building bonds, collaboration and cooperation, and team capabilities (Goldman, 2002).

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The Relationship between Leadership Style, Task and contextual performance.

Several studies reported that transformational leadership affects job performance (task and contextual performance). In this regard, Chandrasekara (2018) asserted transformational leadership is a good predictor of overall job performance. Widodo and Mawarto, (2020) explained that this effect was due to transformational leadership is distinguished by the ability of leaders to articulate a shared vision of the future, intellectually stimulate employees, and pay attention to individual differences in employees. Beside, transformational leadership is also has behaviors that motivate employees to transcend their interests for the good of the group and confidence. Muhammad, Hamid, Shaikh, Qureshi, and Pahi (2016) claimed that leadership styles which refine abilities of the leaders and assist them to obtain job performance, since transformational directly affects job performance and indirectly through the work engagement as mediator in the relationship. Masa'deh, Obeidat, and Tarhini (2016) investigated the influence of transformational leadership on contextual performance of nurses in Kuala Lumpur. The findings of this study revealed that transformational leadership enabled leaders in the nursing sector to motivate nurses and implemented change effectively.

On the other hand, Richards (2020) suggests that transactional leadership remains useful as an approach to meeting short-term goals and completing tasks, but that it should be combined with other leadership styles to maximize its effectiveness in organisations. There is differences in empirical evidence about the effects of transformational and transactional leadership on job performance. At the higher council of youth in Jordan, Masa'deh et al., (2016) revealed that

both transformational and transactional leadership styles have significant impact on job performance, and the latter on firm performance.

Singh and Rani (2017) claimed that effective leadership behaviour plays a significant role in affecting the contextual performance, and strong leaders normally tend to outperform weaker leaders. Kalsoom, Ali, and Zubair (2018) concluded that though both leadership styles are having positive relation with employee performance but transactional leadership style has strongly positive correlation with the performance of the employees.

According to the above discussion, the following four hypotheses can be assumed.

Hypothesis H1: Transactional leadership directly affects task performance.

Hypothesis H2: Transactional leadership does not directly affect contextual performance.

Hypothesis H3: Transformational leadership directly affects task performance.

Hypothesis H4: Transformational leadership directly affects contextual performance.

The Relationship between Transactional, Transformational leadership, and Interpersonal Competencies.

Sosik and Megarian (1999) suggested several aspects of emotional intelligence that would facilitate transformational leadership. First, empathy may be necessary for transformational leaders who display individual consideration to followers. Second, emotion management may promote positive affect and confidence in followers expressing and generating new ideas. Third, self-aware leaders may possess a greater than average sense of purpose and meaning. Fourth, those skilled at emotional management are also those more likely to put the needs of others ahead of their own personal needs.

George (2000) argued that interpersonal competencies appeals may be used by transformational leaders for inspirational motivation. Others have pointed out that adherence to professional or moral standards of behavior are common aspects of both EI and transformational leadership (Brown et al., 2006). Sax (2011) provided important findings. He found that social skills and competencies of leaders are predictors of transformational leadership. In addition, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration are predicted by relationship management, while idealized influence attributed correlated to relationship management. Osman (2020) concluded that middle management leaders with high levels of emotional competencies are more likely to adopt transformational leadership and transactional contingent reward trait, since he found a positive statistically significant relationship between emotional competencies, transformational leadership, and overall transactional leadership but, two subcomponents of transactional leadership style showed either negative significant or insignificant relationship. Accordingly:

Hypothesis H5: Transactional leadership affects interpersonal competencies.

Hypothesis H6: Transformational leadership affects interpersonal competencies.

The Mediating Role of Interpersonal competencies in the Relationship

Interpersonal competencies of leaders can increase employ task and contextual performance. In interpersonal competencies, leaders can create proactive behaviors in followers, and this keeps them motivated and ready to perform their duties and do extra-role behaviour (Alajili, 2019; Ouweneel, Le Blanc, Schaufeli, & Van Wijhe, 2012; Reizer, Brender-Ilan, & Sheaffer, 2019). Empirical research has found that transformational leadership can affect followers' performance by affecting their positive emotions (Reizer et al., 2019), and those leaders emotions influence followers' tasks and contextual performance (Goleman, 2002, Organ, 1988). Interpersonal competencies of leaders pay attention to the emotional needs of followers and enhance their positive emotions to affect their behaviors within the organisation (Kaplan et al., 2014; Thiel, Griffith, & Connelly, 2015). Subsequently, interpersonal competencies of leaders has a positive effect on subordinates' job performance (Thiel et al., 2015).

Bacha (2014) suggested that transformational leadership is incompletely connected to only one dimension of job performance, which is task performance. Moreover, researchers such as Manaf (2014) and Walumbwa (2008) designated that the connection between transformational leadership and job performance is an indirect relationship, the study also suggest that this relation is mediated by different variables such as, adaptability cultural trait, identification and efficacy beliefs. Rahman and Ferdausy (2014) reported that transformational leadership was found to fully mediate the relationship between emotional intelligence (intrapersonal and interpersonal competencies) and task performance. Wan, Pan, Peng, and Meng (2022) revealed that subordinates' positive emotions partially mediates the relationship between emotional leadership and subordinates' task performance, as well as, the direct effect plays a greater than the indirect effect in the relationship between emotional leadership and task performance.

Unlike, Shooshtarian (2013) indicated that no direct noteworthy relationship between transactional leadership and job performance, because rewards is most important component for transactional leaders, which they can offer in exchange of achieving a certain task, but the important issue is employees have specific needs to be fulfilled in order to be motivated but once their needs are fulfilled depending to recompense as a stimulus no longer relevant, therefore, employees may be motivated to a specific extent to fulfill their tasks while retaining the other sources of motivation recommended in the job description of transaction leaders (Dessler, 2015; Masa'deh et al, 2016). Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed.

Hypothesis H7: Interpersonal competencies does not mediate the relationship between transactional leadership and task performance.

Hypothesis H8: Interpersonal competencies does not mediate the relationship between transactional leadership and contextual performance.

Hypothesis H9: Interpersonal competencies mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and task performance.

Hypothesis H10: Interpersonal competencies mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and contextual performance.

THEORY OF THE STUDY

In order to understand how to lead organizations of today, it is helpful to understand how leadership theories and styles have evolved over the years and the impact they have on organizations, particularly employees. This study relies on exchange theory. Early psychologists like Gouldner (1960) and Homans (1958) provided visions and principles about the relationship between two or more parties. They claimed that reciprocity or exchange was the basis of the relationship. Blau's (1964) contributions revealed that the norm of exchange is either on the economic basis or on the social basis. Economic exchange is a binding agreement in which both leaders and employees determine in advance what, when, and how exchanged will be conducted, and that it is not based on trust because the performance of contractual obligations can be enforced by the competent authorities. On the other hand, social exchange indicates that the exchange of benefits in exchange relationships takes place on the basis of trust. There is no agreement on what, when and how exchanges will be conducted (Ibukunoluwa, Anuoluwapo, & Agbude, 2015).

Finger 1: Research model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants were faculty members of five largest universities in Libya (Tripoli University, Benghazi University, Sabbha University, Al- Bidaa University, Omar Al- Moktar University, and Al-Jabal Al-Garbi University). Among more than 11000 teaching member, 390 teaching members were randomly selected and filled in an online questionnaire and distributed it. 320 of 350 questionnaire were collected, of which 315 were valid, with a lost rate of 10%.

Regarding the description of the sample, 220 or 70% of them were male, and the percentage of females was 30%. 34-41 years age group is the most employed in the Libyan universities, constituting 37%, followed by the age group of 42-49 who made up 27%. In addition, for

other age groups, more than 50 years group constituted 25%, followed by 26-33 and 18-25 age groups who constituted 10% and 1% respectively. For education level, out of 315 participants, the majority of the participants were master degree 56% while those with doctorate category made up 44%. On the other hand, assistant professor and lecturer of functional class occupied 30% and 25% of respondents respectively, whilst Assistant lecturer accounted for 20%. Lastly, the results of the descriptive analysis revealed that the co-professor and professor groups participated by 13% and 12% respectively.

Measures

Scales adopted in current study were scored on a 5- point Likert. From 1 “strongly disagree “to 5 “strongly agree”. Transactional and transformational leadership were assessed with Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) that is developed by Avolio and Bass (1985). Transactional style has two key factors; they are Contingent Reward (4 items), Active Management- by Exception (4 items). Last style of leadership is passive/Avoidant leadership style, including passive Management- by Exception (4 items) and Laissez- Faire (4 items). Leaders who practice passive (Bass, 1997). Transformational leadership includes five factors, which are Idealised Influence Attributes, Idealised Influence Behaviours, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individual Consideration. Each factor contains four items (Bass, 1997). In current study, Cronbach’s α was 0.901. Interpersonal competencies were assessed with Daniel Goleman’s (2002) revised Emotional intelligence scale which contains social awareness competencies (11 items), such as “The supervisor is attentive to emotional cues and he a good listener”; and relationship management competencies (35 items), such as "The supervisor acknowledges and reward people’s strengths, accomplishments, and development". In this study, Cronbach’s α was 0.881.

Task and contextual performance were measured using Koopmans, Coffeng, Bernaards, Boot, Hildebrandt, and Beek's (2014) developed scale, which contains task performance (7 items), such as "I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time".; and contextual performance (12 items), such as "I took on extra responsibilities". In this study, Cronbach’s α was 0.721.

RESULTS

Check Data

First, the data was examined to process the missing values of the data in a chain mean method in the SPSS program- version 25. Coefficients of both skewness and kurtosis were used to determine the nature of the data distribution. Standard coefficient of skewness should be between (± 1), while kurtosis is between (± 3) (Awang, 2015). The results of the test in Table 1 indicated that the coefficients of both skewness and kurtosis fell within the range (± 1 and ± 3 respectively), therefore it can be considered that the study data follow a normal distribution.

Table 1: Normality Test of the Univariable in the Study

Variable	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistics	Std. Error	Statistics	Std. Error
TF	.330	.137	-1.449	.274
TR	-.238	.137	-.784	.274
Iterp.C	.089	.137	-1.375	.274
TP	-.222	.137	-.541	.274
CP	-.086	.137	-.929	.274

Although the results of the normal distribution test for univariate data indicated that the data follow a normal distribution, this test is not sufficient. In this regard, hair and others (2010) stated that normality test of the multivariate should do, since Mahalanobis test will conduct, and if the Mahalanobis maximum value is less than critical Chi-Square value, then multivariate normality is existing. Table 2 show the maximum of Mahalanobis distnac (7) is greater than critical Chi-Square value (5.99), and therefore, normality of the multivariate was not achieve.

Table 2: Multivariate Normality Test

Mahalanobis distnac		critical Chi-Square value
Maximum	Maximum	
.637	7.005	5.99

Figure 2: Linearity Assumption

Figure 2 shows the linearity assumption while Figure 3 shows homoscedasticity assumption. For the linearity, by examining the scatter plot residuals and predictors using SPSS, the results indicate a straight-line association between independent variables (transformational leadership

transactional leadership, interpersonal competencies) and dependent variables (task performance and contextual performance). Consequently, there was no evidence to challenge the linearity.

Figure 3 shows the results of the homoscedasticity test through scatter plot diagrams of standardised residuals. These results indicate that homoscedasticity exists in the set of IVs (TF and TR) and the variance of the DV (TP and CP). Furthermore, a visual inspection of the distribution of residuals suggests an absence of heteroscedasticity as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Homoscedasticity Assumption

The multicollinearity test was used to investigate the correlation between independent variables the coefficients of which should not exceed 5.00 and tolerance levels should be in excess of .20 (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010). Table 3 shows the results of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). It reveals that all values of VIF are less than 5.00, which, means there is no multicollinearity between all the exogenous variables.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Independents Variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance > .2	VIF < 5
TF	.412	2.430
TR	.407	2.458
Interp.C	.973	1.027

Descriptive Statistics for Variables

In this section, means and standard deviations were used to describe whether the degree of practice of transformational leadership and transactional leadership are high or low, as well as the extent to which interpersonal competencies, task performance, and contextual performance levels are high or low in Libyan universities, The mean is an indicator of these levels as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean Levels of Variables

Mean	1- 80	1.81- 2.60	2.61- 3.40	3.41- 4.20	4.21- 5
Level	very poor	poor	middle	high	very high

Table 5 provides a summary of mean and standard deviation of variables. The means of all variables fall in the range of 2.74 – 3.34, and according to Table 4 this means that faculty members indicated that leaders have medium levels of transformational and transactional behaviors, interpersonal competences, task performance, and contextual performance.

On the other hand, table 5 appeared that the correlation coefficients among variables ranged from medium to high to no significant relationship. More specifically, transformational leadership was highly correlated (.76) with interpersonal competencies and moderately (.37) correlated to contextual performance, while it is weakly (.11) linked with task performance. Moreover, there is no evidence to support the association of transactional leadership with transformational leadership (-.101), and contextual performance (.021), but the evidence supports a weak positively relationship with task performance (.172**) and negatively (-.164**) with interpersonal competencies.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics inter-correlation summary

Item	M	S.D.	TL	TR	Interp.C	TP	CP
TL	3.34	.770	1				
TR	3.03	1.057	-.101	1			
Interp.C	2.74	.912	.767**	-.164**	1		
TP	3.13	1.06	.111*	.172**	-.006	1	
CP	2.78	1.14	.367**	.021	.259**	.114*	1

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

From matrix of Factor Score Weights, the results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) of the formative structure in Table 6 revealed that transformational leadership includes three sub-structures: charisma, individual considerations, and inspirational motivation, as it is clear that the formative sub-structure of charisma included the variables (T1, T3, T4, and B5 to B8). Similarly, the results revealed that the sub- formative structure of the individual considerations included three variables: (C9, C11, and C12). Lastly, inspirational motivational consists of (IM14, IM15, and IM16). On the other hand, the results of CFA appeared that formative structure of transactional leadership included to two sub- structure, which are contingent

reward with four variables (CR2, CR3, CR5, and CR6), and Management -by- Exception including four variables, which are MEA7, MEA8, MEA10, and MEA14.

Table 6: Factor Score Weights for Leadership

	ME A14	ME A10	M E A8	M E A7	C R6	C R5	C R3	C R2	IM 16	IM 15	IM 14	IC1 2	IC 11	IC 9	IB8	IB 7	IB 6	IB 5	IT 4	IT2	IT1
ME	.15	.32	.14	.07	.06	.05	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
CR	.01	.02	.01	.01	.35	.31	.04	.06	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
IM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.27	.31	.35	.01	.02	.00	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01
IC	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.01	.01	.22	.47	.08	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01
CH	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.01	.01	.01	.03	.01	.09	.15	.09	.09	.15	.17	.18

Note: ME= Management -by- Exception, CR= Contingent Reward, IM= Inspirational Motivation, IC = Individual Consideration, CH= Charisma

Figure 4: CFA for MLQ

Moreover, Figure 4 explains the fitness indices of MLQ. The results of analysis indicated that all fitness indices achieved the levels of acceptance, meaning the data were fit for CFA. The fitness indices for chi-square (χ^2) and χ^2/df were 352.11 and 1.93 respectively, DF was 182, GFI reached .91, CFI and IFI reached .95, RMSEA reached .05, , and p-value was .000 for the model.

On the other hand, CFA results in Table 7 appeared that interpersonal competencies consist of three- sup constructs, since items (EI16, EI19, EI20, EI21, EI22, EI23, and EI24) grouped under same factor is named empathy and leveraging diversity. Furthermore, the items (EI27 to EI30) collected under the so-called communication competencies. Moreover, items (EI34, EI34, and EI35) grouped under same factor is named leadership competencies. Lastly, conflict management and team capabilities gather items (EI37 to EI40).

Table 7: Factor Score Weights for Interpersonal Competencies

	EI37	EI16	EI40	EI39	EI38	EI35	EI34	EI32	EI30	EI29	EI28	EI27	EI26	EI25	EI24	EI23	EI22	EI21	EI20
Inter.C	.18	.09	.12	.15	.16	.26	.29	.25	.23	.18	.20	.22	.19	.10	.15	.08	.20	.17	
Em&Ld	.55	.01	.36	.46	.46	.02	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	
CC	.03	.02	.02	.03	.03	.51	.58	.49	.04	.03	.03	.04	.03	.02	.02	.01	.03	.05	
LC	.01	.01	.02	.01	.01	.02	.02	.01	.49	.40	.44	.47	.01	.01	.01	.00	.01	.01	
CM&TC	.01	.17	.01	.01	.01	.02	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	.34	.18	.27	.14	.36	.31	

Inter.C= Interpersonal competencies, Em&LD= empathy and leveraging diversity, CC= communication competencies, LC= leadership competencies, CM&TC= conflict management and team capabilities.

Moreover, Figure 5 explains the fitness indices of interpersonal competencies. The results of analysis indicated that all fitness indices achieved the levels of acceptance, meaning the data were fit for CFA. The fitness indices for chi-square (χ^2) and χ^2/df were 199.85 and 1.17 respectively, DF was 170, GFI, CFI and IFI exceed .90, RMSEA reached .02, and p-value was.058 for the model.

Figure 5: CFA for Interpersonal Competencies

For task performance and contextual performance, the results of CFA referred that both constructs were first- order, since task performance included four items (TP1, TP2, TP4, and TP5), while contextual performance had six items (CP1 to CP6) as it is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Factor Score Weights for Task Performance and Contextual Performance

	CP6	CP5	CP4	CP3	CP2	CP1	TP5	TP4	TP2	TP1
JP	.059	.073	.076	.070	.096	.055	.116	.054	.143	.086
CP	.229	.281	.293	.270	.371	.212	.009	.004	.011	.007
TP	.007	.008	.008	.008	.011	.006	.520	.240	.638	.385

JP= Job performance, CP= Contextual performance, TP= Task performance.

Moreover, Figure 6 appeared that all fitness indices achieved the levels of acceptance, meaning the data were fit for CFA. The fitness indices for chi-square (χ^2) and χ^2/df were 61.43 and 1.86 respectively, DF was 33, GFI, CFI and IFI exceed .90, RMSEA reached .06, and p-value was .002 for the model

Figure 6: CFA for Task Performance and Contextual Performance

Measurement Model

Measurement model was employed for the purpose of revealing the interrelationships among the structures, as well as in order to verify the study measurements. The results in Figure 7 relieve that all fitness indices are suitable. With regard to relationships, the analysis showed that the relationship between transformational leadership and transactional leadership (p=.45, r= .05) and the relationship between transactional leadership and interpersonal competence (p=.12, r= .12) are insignificant. Furthermore, transformational leadership related to contextual performance more than transactional leadership, while the latter linked to task performance more than transformational leadership.

Figure 7: Measurement Model for Constructions

For convergent validity, the text output explaining the results in Figure 7 is presented in table 9. To achieve convergent validity, composite reliability (CR) should be accessed (.50) and (CR) should be greater than Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Alajili, 2019). Therefore, the results presented in table 9 provide evidence of convergent validity since the CR values for transactional leadership, transformational leadership, interpersonal competencies, task performance, and contextual performance constructs are greater than .50 and AVE values for each exceed .50.

Table 9: Evidence of Convergent Validity for Latent Constructs

Construct	Factor/ Variable	Factor Loading	CR	Standard error	AVE
Transactional Leadership	Contingent Reward	.75	.70	.57	.54
	Management by Exception: Active	.71		.51	
Transformational Leadership	Charisma	.85	.88	.71	.71
	Inspirational Motivation	.84		.70	
	Individual Consideration	.84		.71	
Interpersonal Competencies	Empathy and Leveraging Diversity	.74	.81	.55	.51
	influence and communication	.64		.48	
	Leadership Competencies	.76		.51	
	Conflict Management and Team Capabilities	.72		.51	
Task performance	TP1	.80	.82	.64	.52
	TP2	.73		.53	
	TP4	.69		.47	
	TP5	.67		.45	
Contextual Performance	CP1	.69	.90	.48	.61
	CP2	.89		.79	
	CP3	.74		.55	
	CP4	.84		.71	
	CP5	.73		.54	
	CP6	.75		.56	

CR= Composite Reliability, AVE= Average Variance Extracted

For discriminant validity, two conditions should be met which are: a) Foreter and Larker's criterion which refers to the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is greater than Common Variance (CV); b) Composite Reliability (CR) greater than Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The discriminant validity is explained in Table 10. In Table 10, all requirements were met since the diagonal values (in bold) reflect the square root of AVE of the constructs, while other values are the correlations between the constructs.

Table 10: Discriminant Validity using Foreter and Larker Criteria

Construct	TL	TRL	Intrep.C	TP	CP
TL	.73				
TRL	.05	.84			
Intrep.C	.53	.12	.71		
TP	.23	.38	.32	.72	
CP	.52	.16	.54	.42	.78

TL= transformational leadership, TRL= Transactional leadership, Intrep.C= interpersonal competencies, TP= task performance, CP= contextual performance.

Structural Equation Modeling

To test the hypotheses of this study, two scenarios are used. The first scenario was devoted to studying the bivariate relationships between the study constructs in order to verify that the conditions of indirect relationships (Barron and Kenny, 1986). For the first scenario, the findings of analysis appeared that there are bivariate correlations between transformational leadership, interpersonal competencies, task performance, and contextual performance, and this indicates a possible mediating effect. In contrast, although transactional leadership affects task performance, the findings of the analysis did not provide evidence of its impact on interpersonal competencies and contextual performance, and this would support the non-mediation hypothesis as it is shown in table 11.

Table 11: Bivariate Correlations Summary

Path	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
TRL --> TP	.38	.087	4.313	0.000	Achieved
TRL --> CP	.13	.076	1.724	.085	Un achieved
TRL --> Inrerp. C	.12	.076	1.569	.117	Un achieved
TL --> TP	.22	.057	3.382	0.000	Achieved
TL --> CP	.55	.056	8.371	0.000	Achieved
TL --> Inter. C	.50	.050	7.413	0.000	Achieved
Inrerp. C --> CP	.58	.089	7.760	0.000	Achieved

For the second scenario, since the multivariate variables does not follow a normal distribution, therefore, Bootstrapping has been employed to test direct and indirect hypotheses. So 1000 of Bootstrapping samples and 95% confidents were used. Preliminary the results show that the

bias values were small and this indicates that the differences between Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bootstrapping outcomes were small as it shown in Table 12.

Bootstrap Test

The bootstrapping results referred that the model fit better in 1000 bootstrap samples, as well as, it fit about equally well in 0 bootstrap samples, and It fit worse or failed to fit in 0 bootstrap samples. Therefore, testing the null hypothesis that the model is correct, Bollen-Stine bootstrap $p = .001$.

On the other hand, the results indicated that the bias values are very low (ranging from $-.003$ to 017), which means that there are no differences between the results of ML The rule is the mediation occurs when indirect influence is significant, and partial or full mediation occurs when significant or insignificant of direct effects (Awang, 2015:123).and the results of bootstrap. On the other hand, all fitness indices were met as it shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Structural Model of the Study

For direct hypotheses, findings of Bootstrap Test provided in Table 12, where appear that the estimates to test the impact size, Critical Ratio (C.R), and significance in order to judge the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses. The findings resulted in six direct hypotheses out of eight hypotheses were supported and two was not.

For H1 and H2, the findings confirmed that transactional leadership directly and positively affects task performance and contextual performance ($p > .05$, $C.R. < 1.96$), since effect sizes (Beta β) were (.36) and (.13) respectively, whereas there is no evidence to support the existence of an effect of transactional leadership on interpersonal competencies (H3). Moreover, transformational leadership has positive directly effects on both contextual performance (H5) and interpersonal competencies (H6), where the influence sizes were ($\beta = .32$) and ($\beta = .52$)

respectively, while there is no evidence to support the existence of direct effect of CVX C ررر و دھش § transformational leadership on task performance (H4), ($p = .29$, $\beta = .08$). Lastly, the squared multiple correlation (R^2) for predictors constructs (both leadership styles and interpersonal competencies) of criteria constructs (task and contextual performance) explain (25% and 40% respectively) of its variance.

Table 12: Regression Weights of Each Two-Path Relationship

Hypo.	Exgo.	Path	Endo.	Estimate	S.E.	C.R	P	Result
H1	TRL	-->	TP	.36	.082	4.54	.000	Supported
H2	TRL	-->	CP	.13	.062	2.13	.033	Supported
H3	TRL	-->	Inrerp.C	.08	.064	1.25	.211	Unsupported
H4	TL	-->	TP	.08	.067	1.06	.287	Unsupported
H5	TL	-->	CP	.32	.056	4.56	.000	Supported
H6	TL	-->	Inrerp.C	.52	.051	7.62	.000	Supported

As for indirect effect related to H7, H8, H9, and H10 hypotheses, the bootstrap test findings provided in table 13. The findings supported two indirect hypotheses out of four. These results indicate that there is a mediating effect of interpersonal competencies in the relationship between transformational leadership and both task performance (H9: $p = .003$) and contextual performance (H10: $p = .005$), and given that the direct effect still significant, subsequently the type of mediation is partial. On the other hand, the size of the indirect impact of transformational leadership on contextual performance ($\beta = .19$) is greater than the indirect size on task performance ($\beta = .13$). Given that, the size of the indirect effects occurred in the range between .13 to .26, and therefore it can be judged that the size of the effects is medium (Cohen, 1988).

Moreover, the results did not provide evidence that interpersonal competencies mediate the relationship between transactional leadership and both task performance and contextual performance (H7, H8), as the relationship was not significant ($\beta = .021$, $p = .17$; $\beta = .030$, $p = .16$ respectively).

Table 13: Standardized Indirect Effects

Hypo.	Direct effect size	Indirect effect size	Confidence interval		P-value	Result
			Lower	Upper		
H7	.36	.021	-.013	.077	.17	Unsupported
H8	.36	.030	-.018	.101	.16	Unsupported
H9	.32	.192	.095	.310	.003	Supported
H10	.32	.134	.044	.247	.005	Supported

As long as, interpersonal competencies mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and both task performance and contextual performance, it is imperative to know the type of this mediation through the significance or insignificance of direct effects. Looking at the direct relationships shown in Table 12, we find that the direct impact of transformational leadership on contextual performance is significant ($p = .000$), while its direct impact on task

performance is insignificant ($p = .287$). Given that the direct and indirect impact are statistically significant, and therefore it can be said that interpersonal competencies partially affect the relationship between transformational leadership and contextual performance. In contrast, there is no longer a direct effect of transformational leadership on the task performance ($p = .29$), while the indirect effect is significant, and therefore it can be judged that the interpersonal competencies fully mediate of the relationship between transformational leadership and task performance.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of this study was to assess the relationship that links transformational leadership, transactional leadership, interpersonal competencies, task performance, and contextual performance. The findings of the bootstrap test indicated that the transactional leadership style directly affected task performance, while the effect was not significant on the contextual performance. This result is interesting in that it is consistent with what was reported by (Bass, 1999; Bass & Avolio, 1997), since transactional leader motivates employees by rewards of positive performance, and corrects negative performance by punishment. As expected, the analysis found that transformational leadership had effects on both task and contextual performance. Moreover, transformational leadership had impact on interpersonal competencies, while transactional did not. One explanation is that interpersonal competencies dealing with others are directed to the relations between the leader and his followers, and therefore the behaviours of transactional leaders are formal behaviours, and so this type does not affect or may negatively affect the interpersonal competencies.

According to above, there is no complete agreement between these findings and prior scholars' findings. For instance, Masa'deh (2016) found that both transformational and transactional leadership have significant affect overall job performance (task and contextual performance). Unlike, Rao and Abdul (2015) revealed that transformational leaders had significant impact on team performance, while transactional leadership had negative effect. Moreover, Al-Marnary (2020) indicated that transformational leadership no has directly effect on extra-role behaviour (OCB), but via organizational commitment has significant influence. The complete inconsistency among the findings of the studies may be due to demographic factors or the usage of different measures in measuring variables among studies.

For indirect relationship between predictive constricts and criteria constructs, the findings indicated that only transformational leadership indirectly affects both task performance and contextual performance through interpersonal competencies, while the latter does not mediate with transactional leadership. These findings are consistent with the theory of social-economic exchange (Blau, 1964), since transformational leadership style relatives to extra- role performance such as contextual performance and organizational citizenship behaviour that is often via a mediator such as trust and organization commitment. On the other hand, transactional leadership style related to task performance via reward system (Bass, 1990; Burns, 1976). Although, transformational leadership increases follower motivation and performance more than transactional leadership, but effective leaders use a combination of both

types of leadership (Yuki, 2013). In sum, current study has several essential theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, the study goes beyond past empirical studies, since it studied the effect of transactional leadership on task performance and the influence of transformational leadership on contextual performance rather than studying performance in general. Practically, transformational and transactional of leadership play a different role in the matter of the engagement of employees' contextual and task performance. This means that university officials have to adopt a transactional leadership style if they seek to raise performance efficiency, as well as adopt transformational behaviors if their goal is to urge followers to engage in behavior outside the role.

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